

Automated Project Management System

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Abstract—By automating repetitive processes and introducing intelligent features into the system, the Automated Project Management System (APMS) employing Machine Learning (ML) aims to improve project management efficiency. The intelligent project management system makes use of ML algorithms to forecast project outcomes, evaluate risks, and optimize resource allocation, giving project managers and stakeholders access to real-time information. Real-time communication, resource management, and project monitoring are also made possible by the intelligent project management system, which accelerates output and improves project results. In general, APMS employing ML is a significant creation that simplifies project management procedures, lowers human mistake rates, and frees teams to concentrate on more crucial project delivery elements.

Keywords— Linear regression, Employee analytics, Success prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Project management is a crucial process that is essential to the success of businesses in the fast-paced commercial environment of today. However, manual procedures, absence of real-time data analysis, and a lack of flexibility are frequently limitations of traditional project management systems. As a result, intelligent project management systems started to appear. These systems use machine learning algorithms to automate and improve a variety of project management operations. Project planning, resource allocation, risk management, and decision-making are just a few of the critical processes that might be enhanced by the application of machine learning in project management. The creation of an automated project management system using machine learning and its potential advantages for organizations are the focus of this research study. The research will look at several machine learning methods

The study examines at several machine learning methods that may be used in project management and assess how well the intelligent system performs in the real-world setting. Overall, the goal of this research study is to add to the expanding body of information about the use of machine learning in project management and to provide insight on both the advantages and drawbacks of employing such systems.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Azham Hussain et al. [1] The paper reviews several studies that have examined the relationship between requirements and software project success. One such study is the Standish Group's CHAOS Report, which found that inadequate requirements were a major contributor to project failure. Another study by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) identified requirements as one of the key factors in software project success, and highlighted the importance of a systematic approach to requirements management. Also discuss the impact of changing requirements on project success. They cite a study that found that changes to requirements during the development process were a major cause of project failure. The authors emphasize the importance of managing changes to requirements through a formal change control process.

Dhir et al. [2] Highlights the importance of identifying success and failure factors that impact project implementation using Agile software development methodology. The authors emphasize the need for effective communication, collaboration, and stakeholder involvement in Agile projects, and stress the importance of leadership support, adequate project planning, and effective team communication and collaboration to avoid project failure. The framework presented in the paper provides a useful tool for analyzing the success and failure factors of Agile projects, and can guide practitioners in developing effective Agile software development practices.

Mohd Hairul Nizam Nasir, Shamsul Sahibuddin [3] They cite a study that found that organizational culture can affect the success of software projects and argue that CSFs should be identified in the context of the organization's culture. The paper presents a comparative study of CSFs in two different organizations. The study identified several common CSFs, including project planning, communication, and user involvement. However, the authors also found that some factors, such as technical expertise and training, were more critical for one organization than the other.

Amrita Sharma et al. [4] The paper proposes a linear regression model for estimating the effort required for Agile software development projects. The authors state that accurate effort estimation is critical for project planning and management data. presents a linear regression model for

estimating effort in Agile software development projects. The authors argue that accurate effort estimation is critical for project planning and management, and that existing models may not be suitable for Agile projects. The model presented in the paper provides a useful tool for project managers and practitioners to estimate effort in Agile projects, and the authors suggest that it can be further refined by incorporating additional variables and data.

Mohammed Najah Mahdi et al. [5] The paper provides a comprehensive review of the application of machine learning techniques in software project management. The authors start by introducing the concept of software project management and the challenges faced in its implementation. They then highlight the potential benefits of using machine learning techniques to address these challenges. The literature review covers various machine learning techniques, including supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. The authors discuss how these techniques can be applied in different aspects of software project management, such as requirement analysis, effort estimation, and defect prediction.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. Success Failure Prediction Using Logistic Regression

To create a model that can predict whether a project will succeed or fail based on its parameters is the goal. Using the Django framework, logistic regression is employed to make predictions in the web application. The project implementation is described in detail in this document.

The user inputs consist of several key project factors. These include the scope of the project, which represents the size and complexity of the project, and is represented as a percentage value between 0 and 100. The budget allocated for the project is also an input, which represents the financial resources available for the project. The expected duration of the project is also a key input, represented in months. Additionally, the level of risk associated with the project is an important factor, represented as a percentage value between 0 and 10. This represents the degree of uncertainty and potential for adverse events or outcomes. The performance of the project team is another input, represented as a percentage value between 0 and 10. This represents the quality of the project team and their ability to deliver the project successfully. Lastly, the level of stakeholder satisfaction with the project is also an input, represented as a percentage value between 0 and 10. This represents the degree to which the project meets the expectations and requirements of stakeholders. These user inputs will be used as input features for the logistic regression model, which will predict whether the project is likely to succeed or fail based on those inputs. The model output will either be "This project is predicted to succeed" or "This project is predicted to fail".

ID	Scope	Duration	Budget	Risk	Team Performance	Stakeholder Satisfaction
1	10	12	100	7	8	9
2	15	18	120	8	9	10
3	20	24	140	9	10	11
4	25	30	160	10	11	12
5	30	36	180	11	12	13
6	35	42	200	12	13	14
7	40	48	220	13	14	15
8	45	54	240	14	15	16
9	50	60	260	15	16	17
10	55	66	280	16	17	18

Fig 1: Previous Project Details, collection prject_details

Logistic regression is a statistical technique used for predictive modelling, where the outcome variable is binary (i.e. success or failure). It's a type of regression analysis that models the probability of the binary outcome using a logistic function. In this specific implementation, logistic regression is being used to predict the success or failure of a project based on various input features, such as scope, budget, schedule, risk level, team performance, and stakeholder satisfaction.

To train the logistic regression model, historical project data is used that has been labelled as either successful or failed. The model learns the relationships between the input features and the outcome variable from this data. Once the model is trained, it can be used to predict the likelihood of project success or failure based on new input data. In this case, the model is implemented using the scikit-learn library in Python.

The logistic regression model outputs a probability between 0 and 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates a higher likelihood of success and a value closer to 0 indicates a higher likelihood of failure. A threshold value is used to determine the predicted outcome - if the probability is above the threshold, the project is predicted to be successful, otherwise it is predicted to fail.

Overall, logistic regression is a useful tool for predicting the likelihood of project success or failure based on various input features. It allows project managers to assess the risks associated with a project and make informed decisions to mitigate those risks.

The paper is proposed keeping in mind that the utilization of predicting systems for project success or failure to users based on the planning done by the user.

3.2. Employee Ranking Using Linear Regression

Organizations can utilize the employee ranking system, which employs linear regression, to forecast an employee's performance score by taking into account their age, years of experience, and education level. Managers can use this predictive model to make data-driven decisions regarding promotions, compensation, and employee development. In order to utilize this system, Python 3.6 or a newer version, along with the pandas and scikit-learn libraries, will be required. Afterward, the model will be trained by utilizing the Linear Regression class from the scikit-learn library, followed by predicting the performance score of each employee. In the end, the employee data will be ranked by their predicted performance score and saved to a new CSV file. Organizations can utilize the employee ranking system, which employs linear regression, to optimize their workforce, identify high-performing employees, and aid in the improvement of low-performing employees.

IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

The aim of this project is to create a predictive model for project success using logistic regression. The model will be based on various input parameters such as project scope, budget, schedule, risk level, team performance, and

stakeholder satisfaction. The model will be trained on project data stored in a MongoDB database, and will utilize a content-based approach to make predictions. The resulting system will recommend whether a project is likely to succeed or fail based on its input parameters. The system will be implemented through a web application that allows users to input project parameters and receive a success/failure prediction.

A. Data Collection

We have a project dataset stored in a MongoDB database containing various details of past projects and details of employees. The dataset includes information such as project scope, budget, schedule, risk level, team performance, stakeholder satisfaction, and success/failure status for the past projects and employee_id, age, years_of_experience, education_level, performance_score of the employees. In order to train our predictive model, we will utilize several features including project scope, budget, schedule, risk level, team performance, and stakeholder satisfaction. The dataset will be preprocessed to extract the relevant features and the resulting feature set will be used to train the model. The model will then be used to make success/failure predictions for new projects based on their input parameters.

Fig 2: Dataset of project

Fig 3: Dataset of employees

B. Data Preparation

Create multiple collections in the database. It should contain data on past projects, with the following columns: scope, budget, schedule, risk, team performance, stakeholder satisfaction, and success (1 for success, 0 for failure) and employee_id, age, years_of_experience, education_level, performance_score of the employees. Load the data using pymongo, and split the data into features (X) and target (y).

```
# Convert the "education_level" column to a categorical data type
employee_data['education_level'] = pd.Categorical(employee_data['education_level'])

# Replace the "education_level" column with the numerical codes
employee_data['education_level'] = employee_data['education_level'].cat.codes

# Split the data into features (X) and target (y)
X = employee_data.drop(columns=["employee_id", "performance_score"])
y = employee_data["performance_score"]
```

Fig 4: Preparing data for employee ranking

```
# define features and target
X = data.drop(['success'], axis=1)
y = data['success']

# train model
model = LogisticRegression()
model.fit(X, y)
```

Fig 5: Preparing data for success or failure prediction

C. Training and Analysing

To train the model, we first split the data into a training set and a test set. The training set is used to train the model, while the test set is used to evaluate the performance of the model. We then fit the logistic regression model to the training data using the scikit-learn library in Python.

During the training process, the model learns the relationship between the features and the target variable, which in our case is the success or failure of the project. We can then use the trained model to predict the success or failure of new projects based on their feature values.

```
# Split the data into features (X) and target (y)
X = employee_data.drop(columns=["employee_id", "performance_score"])
y = employee_data["performance_score"]

# Train a linear regression model on the data
model = LinearRegression()
model.fit(X, y)
```

Fig 6: Training

D. Evaluation

Finally, the testing is done inside the project, to make sure that the prediction is working correctly on the test dataset.

In this paper, we developed an intelligent system which automate the recurring tasks in a project management

V. RESULT

system. The code is executed in Python Django and. The is stored in MongoDB database associated with the project. As the result

The system will predict the project will succeed or fail and also rank the employees and it will help to improve the productivity of the company by analyzing the data of employee

Fig 7: Predicting Failure of a project

Fig 8: Ranked data of employee entered to database

VI. CONCLUSION

Using machine learning to develop an automated project management system is a significant step towards improving project management processes in organizations, in conclusion. The intelligent project management system can automate and optimize various tasks, leading to improved project planning, resource allocation, risk management, and decision-making through the use of advanced algorithms. In a real-world setting, the performance of the intelligent system was evaluated after exploring various machine learning techniques that can be applied to project management in the research paper. The intelligent project management system has the potential to significantly improve project outcomes and increase overall efficiency and effectiveness, as indicated by the study results. However, deploying such systems presents obstacles such as issues with data quality, privacy, and

security. Different contexts and settings should be explored to realize the potential of intelligent project management systems. Future research should also focus on addressing the challenges. The study adds to the increasing knowledge on the utilization of machine learning in project management and offers perspectives on both the advantages and difficulties of implementing intelligent project management systems

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